

On the Polymorphism Information Content (PIC) – A Practical Application for the DNA Sequencing Data

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Abstract

All traits of an organism are associated with the genes. Organisms carry genes all of their lifetimes and pass them to the next generations. In genetics, case-control linkage studies named Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) are conducted to establish an association between specific genes, and any medical conditions. It helps to understand the inheritance of traits. In GWAS, genetic markers help us to specify genes, and deliver the required information. The usefulness of a genetic marker depends on the amount of information it provides, which is calculated based on the heterozygosity it holds. To determine the informativity of genetic marker different measures are used. Polymorphism Information Content (PIC) is one of them. It can measure the strength of heterogeneity of a genetic marker that is associated with a gene. A simulated replica of human genome for 2000 individuals in a case-control setting was used in this study. The 16 genes were randomly selected with different features, and the genotype data were enumerated for demonstrating PIC. PIC values of some genes showed strong relation with the allele frequencies. A symmetric relationship between PIC and allele frequencies were observed for the selected genes. Similar association was also noticed for a gene having huge number of SNPs (1500). Although simulated data, this demonstration is expected to provide a significant practical insight for the introductory genetic researchers to whom the access and handling with the real genotype data is a big challenge.

Introduction

Ever thought, about why we don't look the same? or why our all traits are not identical to others, even if we are offspring of the same parent? Though we have some traits similar to our family members or others we also have dissimilarities. This thing happens because of genetic variations in our genome [1]. An organism's all traits are determined by its genome. It is the collection of all genes of an organism. Genes carry blueprints for specific protein synthesis, which is the factor that influences the expression of a trait [2]. Genes are constructed by linear arrangement of the nitrogenous bases known as the deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) sequence[3]. They can have more than one variant or allele [4]. When multiple variants of a gene or DNA sequence is present within a population, polymorphism arises. Large-scale genetic variation can be observed in the human genome [5]. Humans are diallelic which

means an allele pair of the same gene or genotype are required to express a phenotype. More than one genotype can be found for a gene if it has multiple variations of allele or it is polymorphic. Polymorphism contributes to genetic heterogeneity as a polymorphic gene has different combinations of alleles. The establishment of polymorphism and heterogeneity is very important in genetic studies [6-7]. It helps us to identify the distribution of physical characteristics and traits, and risk factors for disease and provides a better understanding of the gene's physical structure. Many observational studies are done in genomics known as Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) to establish a causal relationship between a trait or any medical condition with any specific gene or genes [8]. In a genetic association with case-control study, small variations or single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the entire genome of a large group of people are

More Information

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investigated. Then, SNPs can be identified that occur more frequently in people with a certain disease than those without it. These SNPs are said to be associated with the disease [9]. Such studies are very effective to pinpoint genes likely involved in disease development [10].

Genetic markers are pieces of DNA located at a close distance to the gene on a chromosome and always tend to be inherited with the gene [11]. For this feature, a marker is used to determine the precise inheritance pattern of the gene that has not yet been exactly localized. They play an important role in GWAS as they can capture genetic variations of a gene, establish polymorphism, and enhances our understanding of human health and disease genetics [12-14]. The usefulness of a genetic marker depends on the amount of information it provides which is calculated based on heterozygosity. For genetic studies, different types of genetic markers are used [15]. SNP is a commonly used genetic marker that provides excellent performance in GWAS. One single gene can have a different number of SNPs and the number can be more than 1000 [16]. To determine the informativity of a genetic marker different measures are useful. For example, Polymorphism Information Content (PIC) [17]. Mean heterozygosity (HET) is the basic measure of the informativity of a genetic marker. But this measure is not enough for a situation where both parents have the same heterozygous genotype, and also have half of their offspring with similar heterozygous genotypes like them. Then, it will be difficult to ascertain which allele has a maternal origin, and which allele has a paternal origin. In such situations, PIC is used as a more sophisticated measure of heterozygosity [18].

PIC value captures the heterogeneity and genetic variations for a genetic marker, and establishes polymorphism [19]. Different allele combinations result in different heterogeneity due to polymorphism. Hence, tend to find a relationship between PIC values with allele frequency of genes having different numbers of genetic markers (SNPs).

Materials and Methods

SNP Genotype Data Generation

This study uses the illustrative DNA sequencing data by computer simulation in R Programming language. Data for the 2,000 individuals were generated in a case-control setting, where the individuals were randomly allocated to the cases and controls with equal probability. 16 randomly selected genes having different numbers of SNPs and allele frequencies per gene were selected for the evaluation. The selected genes were given the chorological identification names. Thus, the GENE1, GENE2, GENE3, GENE4, GENE5, GENE6, GENE7, GENE8, GENE9, GENE10, GENE11, GENE12, GENE13, GENE14, GENE15 and GENEX have 1,

2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 1,000 SNPs per gene.

SNP genotype data will be generated randomly using uniform distribution and the allele frequency will lie between 0 to 1. For different combinations of allele frequency of each SNP, genotype frequency will be calculated using the Hardy-Weinberg equation for all probable genotypes. Hardy-Weinberg equation uses the laws of probability to determine the expected frequency of genotypes under certain assumptions. Also, the PIC value will be calculated by using the frequency of the i -th allele in the set of genotypes investigated related to probability.

PIC as a Measure of Polymorphism

In the gene-based SNP genotype DNA sequencing data, different combinations of allele frequencies exist in each SNP for a particular gene. Different combinations of allele frequencies for each SNP will produce different physical structures of genes, hence will produce different PIC values per gene. Based on the allele frequency combination, the genotype frequencies will be different, producing different heterogeneity of each gene. Hence, the measure of allele frequencies is a preliminary measure of SNP-based heterogeneity in a gene.

By the value of PIC, the ability of markers will be determined to establish polymorphism in the sample based on the number of alleles detected and on their frequency distribution.

The estimated PIC value of an m allelic genetic marker will be calculated by the following equation:

$$PIC = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^m p_i^4 - \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{i \neq j}^m p_i^2 p_j^2 \quad (1)$$

where,

m = Total number of alleles detected for a locus of a marker.

p_i = Frequency of the i -th allele in the set of genotypes investigated.

The average informativeness of a genetic marker can be measured by the estimated value of PIC. The strength of this heterogeneity will be further calculated using PIC measures for each gene SNP or SNPs. An average PIC value of > 0.5 , confirms that DNA markers are highly informative. If $0.5 > PIC > 0.25$ then DNA markers are reasonably informative, and if $PIC < 0.25$ then DNA markers are slightly informative. A PIC value near to 1 is most desirable, and it means 100 percent informative DNA marker [20].

In this process, the major and minor alleles will be selected for each SNP of all genes, and the association between PIC value with corresponding major and minor allele frequencies will be assessed.

Results

A. Physical Structures of the Genes

In this study, GENE1, GENE2, GENE3, GENE4, GENE5, GENE6, GENE7, GENE8, GENE9, GENE10, GENE11, GENE12, GENE13, GENE14, and GENE15 have different number of SNPs. For each SNP of a gene, different combinations of allele frequencies between 0 to 1 were observed (Table 1 (appendix 1) and Figure 1(a)). The lowest and the highest allele frequencies were noticed for the SNP13 of GENE15, 0.0895 and 0.9105, respectively (Table 1 (appendix 1) and Figure 1(a)). The second lowest and the second highest allele frequencies were observed for SNP1 in GENE7, 0.1353 and 0.8648 (Table 1 (appendix 1)). The SNPs are diallelic, and all of them have allele frequency more than 0.05. Allele T is the most frequent allele throughout the genes, and hence considered as the major allele for this case. Allele A is only frequent for few SNPs in GENE7, GENE9, GENE10, GENE11, GENE12, GENE13, GENE14, and GENE15, which is the second most frequent allele hence the minor allele. Allele A is most common in GENE13 and has a higher frequency than allele T in 30% of SNPs. Different combination of allele frequency in our sample makes a replica of the

heterogeneous structure of the genome. For different allele frequency combinations in each SNP of these 15 genes the three genotypes (A/T, A/A, and T/T) were there. Their frequency also lies between 0 to 1, shown in Table 2 (appendix 1) and Figure 1(b). The heterozygous genotype (A/T) has the highest frequency of 0.873, found in SNP2 of GENE14 (Table 2 (appendix 1)), and the lowest frequency is 0.04 found in SNP13 of GENE15 (Figure 1(b)). The difference between major allele and minor allele frequency is very low for SNP2 of GENE14 (Figure 2(a)), where genotype A/T has the highest frequency (Table 2(appendix 1)). On the other hand, major and minor allele frequency difference is very high in the case of SNP13 of GENE15 (Figure 2(a)), where the genotype A/T has the lowest frequency (Figure 1(b)). Homozygous genotypes A/A and T/T have the highest frequency of 0.524 for SNP7 of GENE14 (Table 2 (appendix 1)), and 0.8905 for SNP13 of GENE15, respectively (Figure 1(b)). A pattern of genotype frequency for different major and minor allele frequency differences were noticed. When major & minor allele frequency difference starts to increase the frequency of genotype A/T of GENE15 starts to decrease, graphically represented in Figure 2(a).

Figure 1: Properties of a Gene Having 15 SNPs (GENE15): (a) Major Allele Frequency per SNP, (b) Genotype Frequency per SNP, (c) PIC Values per SNP, (d) Scatter Plot of Major & Minor Allele Frequency and PIC Values

B. Heterogeneity of Each Gene based on Allele Frequency

As different allele frequency combinations produces different genotype frequencies that produced different

heterogeneity for each gene. All the SNPs of GENE1, GENE2, GENE3, GENE4, GENE5, GENE6, GENE7, GENE8, GENE9, GENE10, GENE11, GENE12, GENE13, GENE14, and GENE15 have allele frequencies greater than 0.05

for both major and minor. Hence, these SNPs are polymorphic (heterogeneous), and can be used in GWAS. No rare allele were observed for any gene.

Figure 2: Scatter Plot of Major and Minor Allele Frequency Difference and Genotype Frequencies for Two genes: (a) For GENE15 with 15 SNPs, (b) For GENEX with 1000 SNPs

Figure 3: Scatter Plot of Major and Minor Allele Frequency and PIC Value for GENEX Having 1000 SNPs

C. Polymorphism of Genes Based on PIC

PIC values are found from a calculation using allele and genotype frequencies are represented in Table 3 (appendix 1). By the PIC values for each SNP contained in each of the 15 genes, it could be summarized that they are heterogeneous, and provide evidence of the existence of polymorphism in them. The highest PIC value (0.375) is found for SNP5 of GENE10 (Table 3 (appendix 1)), and the lowest PIC value (0.1497) is found for SNP13 of GENE15 (Figure 1(d)). Maximum PIC values for each SNP of these genes fall in the range of 0.25 to 0.5 (Table 3 (appendix 1)). So, they are reasonably heterogeneous and informative. At most 1 or 2 SNPs with PIC values less than 0.25 for GENE5, GRNE7, GENE9, GENE11, and GENE15 were there. As these SNPs are less informative, they may be dropped from the GWAS to ensure the efficient use of markers.

D. Association between PIC and Major & Minor Allele.

An association were be noticed between the major & minor allele frequency difference and the frequency of genotype A/T of GENE15, represented in Figure 2(a).

This association indicates some relation between PIC values with major & minor allele frequencies. From the scatter plot of major and minor allele frequencies with PIC values of GENE15, a bell-shaped curve is found (Figure 1(d)). In this curve, the PIC values start to increase when minor allele frequencies are increasing. On the other hand, a decrease of PIC values were there when the major allele frequency starts to increase. The topmost point of the bell-shaped curve is found for a value of 0.5 (approx.) of both the major and minor alleles, and the PIC value for that point is close to 0.375. In other words, both the minor and major allele frequencies are close to 0.5, the highest PIC values can be found. It is the changing point, where a symmetrical relationship between allele frequency and PIC value is observed.

To find a similar relationship between PIC values with major and minor alleles in genes, where it has a large number of SNPs GENEX (number of SNPs 1,000) were evaluated. Figure 2(b) shows that major and minor allele frequency difference has also a similar

association for this gene with the frequency of genotype A/T as observed for the other genes (Figure 2(a)). A bell-shaped scatter plot represented in Figure 3 shows that major and minor allele frequency and PIC value have also similar associations, where the topmost point represents the highest PIC value, close to 0.375, and allele frequencies are found close to the value 0.5 for this point. This is the changing point where a symmetrical relationship between allele frequencies and PIC values can be observed for GENEX as observed for the GENE15 (Figure 1(d)).

Discussion

Genes with small, medium, or higher numbers of SNPs show an association between PIC value with both the major and minor allele frequencies. When both the major and minor allele frequencies are approximately 0.5, the PIC value is the highest, which is 0.375 in this case. It can be considered as the symmetrical changing point from where PIC values start to fall for both major and minor alleles where almost similar PIC values were found for them.

Though this is a small-scale analysis because of lots of limitations (funding to obtain real data, LAB-server facilities, etc.), this will provide a preliminary complete structure for conducting bioinformatical research for such applications. The results of this study analysis would be the same if real data were used. Because of the unavailability of real data, lack of laboratory facilities, financial limitations, and technical limitations real data could not be considered.

Conclusions

The study considers a practical demonstration of PIC as a heterogeneity measure of SNP in human genome. The simulated replica of gene-based SNP genotype data were applied for this purpose. The PIC values were calculated per SNP for a given gene with different structures in terms of number of SNPs, allele frequencies etc. The results shows that different PIC values were observed per SNP in a given gene as there is a difference in the combinations of allele frequencies. A symmetrical relationship can be noticed between them at a point, where allele frequencies are close to 0.5 and PIC values are close to 0.375. This point is the changing point as it gives the highest PIC value, and PIC values start to decrease if major allele frequency increases or minor allele frequency decreases. Despite of using a simulated data, this demonstration will be the same if applied for the real genotype data.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix 1

Table 1: Allele Frequency of the Genes Having Number of SNPs from 1 to 14

Gene Name	Allele Name	Allele frequencies													
		SNP1	SNP2	SNP3	SNP4	SNP5	SNP6	SNP7	SNP8	SNP9	SNP10	SNP11	SNP12	SNP13	SNP14
GENE1	A	0.4143													
	T	0.5858													
GENE2	A	0.2605	0.3488												
	T	0.7395	0.6513												
GENE3	A	0.3158	0.3403	0.375											
	T	0.6843	0.6598	0.625											
GENE4	A	0.2025	0.3805	0.303	0.366										
	T	0.7975	0.6195	0.697	0.634										
GENE5	A	0.155	0.2605	0.3768	0.2855	0.32									
	T	0.845	0.7395	0.6233	0.7145	0.68									
GENE6	A	0.2305	0.409	0.436	0.2763	0.319	0.3358								
	T	0.7695	0.591	0.564	0.7238	0.681	0.6643								
GENE7	A	0.1353	0.2415	0.2445	0.3233	0.3488	0.3283	0.6748							
	T	0.8648	0.7585	0.7555	0.6768	0.6513	0.6718	0.3253							
GENE8	A	0.2348	0.3118	0.209	0.3968	0.3563	0.3685	0.3773	0.4493						
	T	0.7653	0.6883	0.791	0.6033	0.6438	0.6315	0.6228	0.5508						
GENE9	A	0.1583	0.182	0.3075	0.3563	0.3283	0.319	0.366	0.554	0.436					
	T	0.8418	0.818	0.6925	0.6438	0.6718	0.681	0.634	0.446	0.564					
GENE10	A	0.2893	0.2485	0.203	0.2703	0.5053	0.415	0.3108	0.3743	0.3215	0.4143				
	T	0.7108	0.7515	0.797	0.7298	0.4948	0.585	0.6893	0.6258	0.6785	0.5858				
GENE11	A	0.148	0.2975	0.413	0.4115	0.603	0.4063	0.4455	0.3773	0.366	0.3215	0.2703			
	T	0.852	0.7025	0.587	0.5885	0.397	0.5938	0.5545	0.6228	0.634	0.6785	0.7298			
GENE12	A	0.4325	0.3978	0.2773	0.4548	0.632	0.324	0.3718	0.539	0.4675	0.3695	0.2753	0.386		
	T	0.5675	0.6023	0.7228	0.5453	0.368	0.676	0.6283	0.461	0.5325	0.6305	0.7248	0.614		
GENE13	A	0.3958	0.3465	0.24	0.2993	0.274	0.3325	0.427	0.5495	0.6445	0.5185	0.5178	0.1795	0.28	
	T	0.6043	0.6535	0.76	0.7008	0.726	0.6675	0.573	0.4505	0.3555	0.4815	0.4823	0.8205	0.72	
GENE14	A	0.4558	0.4505	0.3558	0.381	0.3825	0.2083	0.7173	0.3065	0.3605	0.3463	0.2953	0.4115	0.2605	0.2773
	T	0.5443	0.5495	0.6443	0.619	0.6175	0.7918	0.2828	0.6935	0.6395	0.6538	0.7048	0.5885	0.7395	0.7228

Table 2: Genotype Frequency of the Genes Having Number of SNPs from 1 to 14

Gene Name	Genotype Name	Genotype frequencies													
		SNP1	SNP2	SNP3	SNP4	SNP5	SNP6	SNP7	SNP8	SNP9	SNP10	SNP11	SNP12	SNP13	SNP14
GENE1	A/A	0.182													
	A/T	0.4645													
	T/T	0.3535													
GENE2	A/A	0.162	0.1935												
	A/T	0.197	0.3105												
	T/T	0.641	0.496												
GENE3	A/A	0.1945	0.017	0.0165											
	A/T	0.2425	0.6465	0.717											
	T/T	0.563	0.3365	0.2665											
GENE4	A/A	0.0865	0.0085	0.0805	0.1195										
	A/T	0.232	0.744	0.445	0.493										
	T/T	0.6815	0.2475	0.4745	0.3875										
GENE5	A/A	0.1035	0.0605	0.073	0.0605	0.173									
	A/T	0.103	0.4	0.6075	0.45	0.294									
	T/T	0.7935	0.5395	0.3195	0.4895	0.533									
GENE6	A/A	0.142	0.121	0.224	0.101	0.15	0.028								
	A/T	0.177	0.576	0.424	0.3505	0.338	0.6155								
	T/T	0.681	0.303	0.352	0.5485	0.512	0.3565								
GENE7	A/A	0.0615	0.054	0.0145	0.053	0.1935	0.038	0.4945							
	A/T	0.1475	0.375	0.46	0.5405	0.3105	0.5805	0.3605							
	T/T	0.791	0.571	0.5255	0.4065	0.496	0.3815	0.145							
GENE8	A/A	0.048	0.1355	0.0055	0.119	0.023	0.062	0.048	0.191						
	A/T	0.3735	0.3525	0.407	0.5555	0.6665	0.613	0.6585	0.5165						
	T/T	0.5785	0.512	0.5875	0.3255	0.3105	0.325	0.2935	0.2925						
GENE9	A/A	0.1165	0.0515	0.0965	0.023	0.038	0.15	0.1195	0.1745	0.224					
	A/T	0.0835	0.261	0.422	0.6665	0.5805	0.338	0.493	0.759	0.424					
	T/T	0.8	0.6875	0.4815	0.3105	0.3815	0.512	0.3875	0.0665	0.352					
GENE10	A/A	0.138	0.056	0.1175	0.0415	0.2995	0.173	0.035	0.218	0.1125	0.182				
	A/T	0.3025	0.385	0.171	0.4575	0.4115	0.484	0.5515	0.3125	0.418	0.4645				
	T/T	0.5595	0.559	0.7115	0.501	0.289	0.343	0.4135	0.4695	0.4695	0.3535				

GENE1 1	A/A	0.0355	0.0585	0.1815	0.0445	0.2215	0.0985	0.2685	0.048	0.1195	0.1125	0.0415			
	A/T	0.225	0.478	0.463	0.734	0.763	0.6155	0.354	0.6585	0.493	0.418	0.4575			
	T/T	0.7395	0.4635	0.3555	0.2215	0.0155	0.286	0.3775	0.2935	0.3875	0.4695	0.501			
GENE1 2	A/A	0.1	0.0355	0.145	0.2295	0.3	0.0095	0.19	0.1245	0.2405	0.0265	0.0385	0.0925		
	A/T	0.665	0.7245	0.2645	0.4505	0.664	0.629	0.3635	0.829	0.454	0.686	0.4735	0.587		
	T/T	0.235	0.24	0.5905	0.32	0.036	0.3615	0.4465	0.0465	0.3055	0.2875	0.488	0.3205		
GENE1 3	A/A	0.099	0.101	0.011	0.029	0.115	0.0065	0.1115	0.4955	0.503	0.1505	0.328	0.092	0.0215	
	A/T	0.5935	0.491	0.458	0.5405	0.318	0.652	0.631	0.108	0.283	0.736	0.3795	0.175	0.517	
	T/T	0.3075	0.408	0.531	0.4305	0.567	0.3415	0.2575	0.3965	0.214	0.1135	0.2925	0.733	0.4615	
GENE1 4	A/A	0.1795	0.014	0.15	0.098	0.1175	0.12	0.524	0.154	0.0585	0.164	0.017	0.0715	0.065	0.15
	A/T	0.5525	0.873	0.4115	0.566	0.53	0.1765	0.3865	0.305	0.604	0.3645	0.5565	0.68	0.391	0.2545
	T/T	0.268	0.113	0.4385	0.336	0.3525	0.7035	0.0895	0.541	0.3375	0.4715	0.4265	0.2485	0.544	0.5955

Table 3: PIC values of the 14 genes having number of SNPs from 1 to 14.

Gene Name	PIC Values													
	SNP1	SNP2	SNP3	SNP4	SNP5	SNP6	SNP7	SNP8	SNP9	SNP10	SNP11	SNP12	SNP13	SNP14
GENE1	0.3675													
GENE2	0.3111	0.3511												
GENE3	0.3387	0.3482	0.3589											
GENE4	0.2708	0.3603	0.3332	0.3564										
GENE5	0.2276	0.3111	0.3593	0.3248	0.3405									
GENE6	0.2918	0.3666	0.3709	0.3199	0.3401	0.3466								
GENE7	0.2066	0.2992	0.3012	0.3418	0.3511	0.3438	0.3426							
GENE8	0.2947	0.3371	0.276	0.3641	0.3535	0.3571	0.3595	0.3724						
GENE9	0.2309	0.2534	0.3352	0.3535	0.3438	0.3401	0.3564	0.3721	0.3709					
GENE10	0.3266	0.3037	0.2712	0.3166	0.375	0.3677	0.3366	0.3587	0.3411	0.3675				
GENE11	0.2204	0.3306	0.3673	0.367	0.3642	0.3661	0.372	0.3595	0.3564	0.3411	0.3166			
GENE12	0.3704	0.3643	0.3205	0.3729	0.357	0.3421	0.358	0.3735	0.3739	0.3574	0.3194	0.3617		
GENE13	0.3639	0.3503	0.2983	0.3315	0.3187	0.3454	0.3696	0.3725	0.3532	0.3747	0.3747	0.2512	0.3219	
GENE14	0.373	0.3725	0.3533	0.3604	0.3608	0.2754	0.3233	0.3348	0.3548	0.3502	0.3296	0.367	0.3111	0.3205

